

Where Are the Scientists?: Representation of Students with Science Backgrounds in MLIS Programs in Canada

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Abstract

This critical literature review identifies the motivations of students entering the Library and Information Studies/Science (LIS) profession and associated Master's (MLIS) programs, the current knowledge of students and librarians with science backgrounds in LIS fields, and the intersections of these two areas into recruitment research for LIS professionals with science backgrounds. A critical literature review was conducted, with clearly relevant literature included. In general, incoming MLIS students tend to be in the process of changing careers, and they are motivated to pursue LIS due to a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic factors related to their individual contexts. While educational diversity benefits the entire discipline and workforce, science librarianship specifically benefits from having MLIS graduates with science backgrounds. It is expected that the increased complexity and data services focus of science librarianship may also be well served by those with science backgrounds. Recruitment suggestions for increasing the representation of students with science backgrounds in MLIS programs tend to be mere concepts or substantial program investments, without many practical recommendations or real-life examples. Notably, there is a gap in investigations for the Canadian context, and so an exploratory investigation of the motivations and aspirations of students in Canadian MLIS programs, beyond the literature review presented here, should be conducted in the future with a specific focus on identifying and investigating the population of students coming into these programs with science education backgrounds.

Keywords

Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS), educational background, science background, motivation, recruitment, career choices, graduate study, MLIS students

Introduction

With increased emphasis and focus on science, technology, engineering, mathematics (STEM) and affiliated applied science fields in our society (Clarke & Kim, 2018), Canada is seeing an increase in post-secondary enrollment in STEM-related fields (Statistics Canada, 2022). As these students move through their undergraduate and college degrees, there is an expected and anecdotal increase in Master's-level Library and Information Studies/Science (MLIS) students with STEM and applied science backgrounds (e.g., as stated by Kuruppu [2006]). However, MLIS student educational backgrounds are predominantly in English, history, and education studies prior to attending American Library Association (ALA)-accredited schools in North America (Beck & Callison, 2006; Clarke & Kim, 2018; Lo et al., 2015). Though these predominant educational backgrounds inevitably imply the underrepresentation of several other disciplines, such as fine arts and business, the representation of science backgrounds is considered especially low (Harrick & Fullington, 2017; Lantzy & Matlin, 2021; Walker, 2011) and is especially so for students with engineering backgrounds (Winston, 2000). Throughout the literature, "MLIS" is used to denote ALA-accredited Master's-level Library and Information programs and this review does the same.

Several Library and Information Studies/Science (LIS) professional positions seek MLIS graduates with STEM and applied science backgrounds and experiences, most notably in science, technology, engineering, and similar subject-specific academic librarian positions (Beck & Callison, 2006; Eells, 2006; Fritzler, 2006; Hallmark & Lembo, 2003; Kuruppu, 2006; Lo et al., 2015; Raszewski, 2011; Sterner, 2020). There is also a growth of research and data services LIS positions throughout academia that would benefit from MLIS and STEM combined skill sets (ACRL, 2022; Bishop et al., 2021; Bishop et al., 2023; Clarke & Kim, 2018; Dali & Caidi, 2016; Dennie, 2014; Eells, 2006; Kuruppu, 2006; Sterner, 2020; Smith, 2006). Additionally, increased educational diversity in MLIS programs leads to diverse perspectives in LIS as a profession, resulting in growth in the development of LIS practice and research (Clarke & Kim, 2018). Coupled with the aging or "graying" of the LIS field (Ard, 2006; Kuruppu, 2006; Level & Blair, 2006; Pellack, 2006; Taylor et al., 2011) and overall concerns about librarian recruitment (Beck & Callison, 2006), there are not enough qualified candidates applying to positions well-suited to MLIS graduates with science backgrounds, such as science librarianship (Sterner, 2020; Walker, 2011). It is difficult to know the situation in Canada, as an analysis of Canadian MLIS educational backgrounds has only

been done as part of larger international studies, without a specific focus on STEM and applied science backgrounds, and with data more than five years old (see, for example, Ho et al., 2018; Lo et al., 2015; Lo et al., 2017; Oguz et al., 2015; Weech & Konieczny, 2007). Knowing the current state of student educational backgrounds in Canadian MLIS programs and student motivations for enrolling, particularly for those with science backgrounds, will enable improved recruitment overall, but specifically from STEM and applied science fields.

This literature review will aim to explore the current understanding of the motivations of students entering the LIS profession and MLIS programs, the current knowledge of students and librarians with science backgrounds in LIS fields, and the intersections of these two areas in the recruitment research for LIS professionals with science backgrounds. Research questions for this literature review are:

1. What are the motivations for entering MLIS programs and the LIS field in general?
2. What are the educational backgrounds of students enrolled in Canadian MLIS programs or MLIS programs generally? What is the proportion of students with STEM and applied science backgrounds?
3. Why have students with STEM and applied science backgrounds enrolled in MLIS programs, specifically in Canada if available, and how do their motivations compare with their peers?
4. What recruitment strategies are being used or suggested to increase interest in MLIS programs for people with STEM and applied science backgrounds? By extension, what recruitment strategies should be used for Canadian MLIS programs?

Method

This review was conducted as an embedded critical literature review. The original research question was “Why did MLIS students with science backgrounds in Canada enroll in their MLIS program?” and was broadened to consider:

- Who tends to enroll in MLIS programs?
- Why do students enroll in MLIS programs?
- What do graduates of science programs tend to do after their degrees, and what proportion go into an MLIS program?
- What do MLIS students with science backgrounds do after their

MLIS degree?

- Are there roles and positions that are uniquely satisfied by MLIS graduates with science backgrounds?

These connected research questions guided the search and relevance criteria for this literature review, including:

- MLIS programs, LIS graduate programs, Library and Information Science students, Library and Information Studies students, science librarians, science and technology librarians, STEM librarians
- Motivations, student motivation
- Educational background, science background, science educational background
- North America, Canada, American Library Association, ALA

Relevance criteria evolved during the course of the review due to a lack of existing research on Canadian LIS programs, students, and professionals regarding educational background and motivation. Any mention of science educational backgrounds for LIS students or professionals in North America led to inclusion. For related materials without these specific considerations, inclusion was based on relevance to a Canadian context (i.e., Canadian or North American) and time of publication (i.e., within the last 5 years). Resources were found by searching via the University of Alberta Library catalogue, SAGE Journals, Science & Technology Libraries journal catalogue, and Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship journal catalogue. Searches were also conducted via Google Scholar. 44 resources were included in the review, each addressing one or more of the research questions above.

Using both discipline-specific catalogues and a large indexing database (Google Scholar), this review may be comprehensive specifically in regards to the estimated portion of LIS students who have science backgrounds, their representation in the LIS workforce, and how this demographic is recruited into LIS.

A limit of this literature review is the potential bifurcation of search results based on the naming of ALA-accredited graduate programs: namely, studies needing to choose between specifying an MLIS or a Master of Information (MI), degrees increasingly awarded by iSchools (iSchools, n.d.). MI degrees were not explicitly investigated in this literature review, and they were not addressed in any of the resources focusing on students currently in LIS programs. While this only affects a subset of the interrelated research questions, it is worth noting that a broader set of search terms specifically including MI de-

degrees or a narrower investigation specifically on MI degrees may have different conclusions than those presented here. Another limitation of this review is that it does not encompass all existing research on the motivations of LIS students and professionals. The conclusions presented here regarding LIS student and professional motivations may be considered a critical summary instead of a comprehensive review.

Motivations to Enter MLIS Program and LIS Professions

The motivations to enter an MLIS program are linked with the motivations to enter the LIS profession. In general, career decisions for undergraduate students are motivated by demographic, social, environmental, and cultural factors (Thomas et al., 2023). However, many prospective LIS professionals enter an MLIS program as a second or even third career (Ard, 2006; Beck & Callison, 2006; Dukic, 2019) and for many it is not their first choice for a graduate program (Ho et al., 2018). In particular, Taylor et al. (2011) found that over half of MLIS students decided on LIS after completing their first degree, and a third made the call more than five years after completing their first degree. There is a noted increase in second-career librarians coming from other occupational areas (Dukic, 2019), and Canada leads this trend (Lo et al., 2015). Entering into the field of LIS professions is often considered serendipitous or accidental (Hallmark & Lembo, 2003). However, once a prospective student has encountered the field, their decision to enter LIS is purposeful and fulfills the needs of their particular context and aspirations (Lo et al., 2017).

Given that MLIS students come from a variety of backgrounds and enter their programs at different ages, life stages, and career stages, it is surprising that students across borders and cultures report similar motivations in pursuing an MLIS. In general, MLIS students are motivated by a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Dukic, 2019; Moniarou-Papaconstantinou et al., 2015; Taylor et al., 2011). Intrinsic factors refer to the desires and interests of the person, including an interest in library work, a love of books and reading, enjoyment in providing service, an interest in technology, or a desire for personal learning and career development. Extrinsic factors are impressed upon the person from their current context, including employment stability, job security, and availability of employment opportunities. Certain MLIS student populations tend to lean towards more extrinsic or more intrinsic factors. Lo et al. (2015) identified that MLIS students at the University of British Columbia were mostly motivated by extrinsic factors related to career progression, likely

due to an MLIS being required for many higher-level LIS positions. However, Dukic (2019) revealed that those in online and part-time MLIS programs who are already employed in an LIS field will lean towards extrinsic motivations, while those employed in non-LIS positions lean towards intrinsic motivations. This finding might imply that in Canada, or at least at the University of British Columbia, many MLIS students are already working in an LIS setting. Therefore, current employment status and occupational area are relevant when considering student motivations.

Other experiences and personal contexts have also been found to play significant roles in students enrolling in an MLIS program. In particular, previous exposure to libraries and library work is an important factor in recruitment into LIS (Dukic, 2019; Lo et al., 2015; Simon & Taylor, 2011), with approximately 40% of students citing exposure as a significant positive influence on their decision (Ho et al., 2018; Taylor et al., 2011). Looking to change careers is another strong motivator (Dukic, 2019; Lo et al., 2015), both from the perspective of current careers driving students away due to burn-out or general disappointment and of LIS being appealing: in particular, that libraries are considered “safe-haven-like” (Lo et al., 2017, p. 431). Of interest is that Lo et al. (2017) found a third facet of changing careers that motivated students to enroll in MLIS programs: their anticipated contribution to the field through professional skills transfer. This finding speaks to the benefit of not only educational background diversity in LIS but also occupational experience diversity.

The diversity of LIS professions is also a factor in drawing students to MLIS programs. There is a rise in interest in special and subject libraries (Taylor et al., 2011); this rise and the broadening of the LIS field to nontraditional roles such as consulting, information technology, and data modelling (Gordon, 2008) both speak to a widening scope of positions for MLIS students to investigate and pursue.

Changes in MLIS programs themselves are also encouraging enrollment from students who otherwise would not have considered LIS as an option. With the rise in online, ALA-accredited MLIS programs in North America, there is an increase in accessibility on multiple fronts. Most notably, asynchronous learning allows for flexibility and does not require students to relocate—both of which allow students to work alongside their studies. In Canada specifically, there are options for hybrid (e.g., University of Western Ontario) and online (e.g., University of Alberta) MLIS programs. Oguz et al. (2015) noted from a survey of 910 students in Canada and the United States who completed at least one online MLIS course that the main motivators for stu-

dents to enroll in online programs were convenience, flexibility, predisposition to online learning, and the fact that it was the only viable option for them to pursue an MLIS. In particular, 81.6% of fully online students reported that they chose an online MLIS program instead of an in-person or hybrid option because it allowed them to keep their current employment (p. 221). Given that very few studies of MLIS student motivation account for or incorporate program delivery mode in their analysis (exceptions include Detlefsen, 2004; Dukic 2019; Oguz et al., 2015; Piper & Wilairat, 2022; Taylor et al., 2011), it is worth noting that online students may be less motivated by a career change than their hybrid and onsite counterparts. Online students may therefore be more motivated by their anticipated contribution to LIS via the skills they have developed in their current careers. Investigating differences between online and onsite MLIS populations is therefore a critical area when considering MLIS student demographics and motivations.

Despite similarities and trends among MLIS students, there are significant differences between countries (Ho et al., 2018). The cultural dimensions attached to the LIS profession, students pursuing an MLIS, and the subject area of LIS all play a role and are influenced by dimensions such as power distance, individualism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term orientation, and indulgence. Therefore, it cannot be assumed that student motivations in one country mirror those of students in another, even if they are geographically close. MLIS programs with culturally diverse students will also likely encounter differences along cultural lines. Canadian graduate programs, including MLIS programs, tend to have an international student contingent of at least 20% on average (Statistics Canada, 2023), with online MLIS program options that are accessible across the globe. This reality suggests cultural dimensions are significant when assessing student motivations for Canadian MLIS programs, as not all students are from or currently reside in Canada.

STEM Backgrounds in MLIS Programs and LIS Professions

With overarching concerns of LIS position vacancies due to the aging of professionals in the field (Beck & Callison, 2006), MLIS recruitment strategies have long been focused on “targeting job-starved disciplines,” such as history and English, to replenish the LIS workforce, specifically in libraries (Ard, 2006, p. 245). This has led to a lack of recruitment efforts in STEM and applied science fields, among others.

Research into the presence of scientists and people with science back-

grounds in MLIS programs and LIS professions is difficult to compare due to varying definitions of which disciplines count as “science.” Additionally, some studies provide a transparent and specific definition, while others do not. The range of applications of “science” in large studies of MLIS students or science librarians include: science and engineering librarians (Winston, 2000); science and technology librarians, excluding medical librarians (Beck & Calliston, 2006); STEM liaison librarians (Bishop et al., 2023); science and technology librarians in health sciences, natural sciences, life sciences, and physical sciences (Eells, 2006); and physical sciences, life sciences, earth/environmental sciences, and mathematics but not applied sciences such as engineering, health science, computer science, and science education (Walker, 2011). Clearly, more disciplines being counted as part of “science” will increase the number of students and professionals considered, potentially giving a false impression of high enrollment and representation rates of people with science backgrounds. Alternatively, making the definition of “science” too narrow would artificially decrease those same values. Being clear about what is being considered as “science” is paramount when considering the educational background of MLIS students and LIS professionals.

With this range of definitions in mind, there is also difficulty in identifying what the actual proportions are of MLIS students and LIS professionals with science backgrounds. Two levels of analysis are clear in the literature: the proportion of people with science backgrounds in LIS overall, and the proportion of people with science backgrounds in science librarianship specifically. In LIS generally, it is accepted that there are few people with science backgrounds (Harrick & Fullington, 2017; Lantzy & Matlin, 2021; Level & Blair, 2006). This conclusion is supported by Walker’s (2011) analysis of 2653 MLIS students in the United States, in which only 133 were found to have a science background: i.e., 5–6% of all students. However, note that Walker used a restrictive definition of “science,” excluding engineering and computer science, which are commonly considered part of the STEM umbrella. More recent, albeit smaller, studies have found more than twice that representation: Clarke & Kim (2018) found 11% of MLIS students from seven schools in the United States had science backgrounds; Ho et al. (2018) found up to 18%; and Dukic (2019) found 21.7% for online students already working in LIS and 13.8% for those not already working in LIS. It is still difficult to compare these values given the unknown definition of “science” in some of these studies. However, it is clear that the often-quoted 5–6% from Walker (2011) is a lower limit, and the true value is likely over 10%. In science librarianship, comparisons

between studies of educational background are likewise difficult to make. This difficulty is due to the same issue of unclear or differing definitions of “science” when considering science backgrounds, in addition to inconsistent definitions of “educational background,” where some studies only considered formal degrees (i.e., Bachelor of Science, Master of Science, Doctor of Philosophy) and others considered any formal experience in science sufficient, such as taking a single undergraduate science course (Hackenburg & Chu, 2002).

Despite these issues, it is generally accepted that there are more individuals with science backgrounds in science librarian positions, or aspiring to fill these positions, than in LIS more generally (Clarke & Kim, 2018; Walker, 2011). This reality is unique to science librarianship, as other subject-specific librarian professions tend to have educational backgrounds more similar to the general LIS field (Clarke & Kim, 2018). From the literature, differences in definitions and sample sizes make it difficult to determine a definite value. However, Winston’s (2000) finding that 32.2% of science librarians have a formal science background and Hackenburg & Chu’s (2002) finding that 60% of science librarians have at least some science experience are most often cited. More recent studies have found science librarians with science backgrounds comprise 66.6% (Beck & Calliston, 2006), 50% (Eells, 2006), 28.57% (Stern-er, 2020), or 49% (Bishop, 2023) of the science librarian profession, and 63% for physical science librarians specifically (Ortega & Brown, 2005). It is likely, given these findings, that at least one-third of science librarians have a science background, and that physical science librarians likely have a higher rate. This implies that there is indeed a higher ratio of people with science backgrounds in science librarianship than in LIS in general. It has been suggested that the higher rate of LIS professionals with science backgrounds implies that there may be a higher rate of men in science librarianship than in LIS in general (Beck & Callison, 2006). However, most studies find that the percentage of women in science librarianship is comparable to that in LIS for the same time period (Eells, 2006; Piper & Wilairat, 2022; Walker, 2011) or is significantly higher (Raszewski, 2011). It is worthwhile to track demographic information such as gender to benchmark with these findings.

When compared to post-secondary populations more generally, Clarke & Kim (2018) argue that the LIS profession historically does not reflect the United States undergraduate population. Canada has a growing population of people with post-secondary education compared to previous generations and is keeping pace with other countries that are part of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, but it is falling behind in re-

gard to graduate degree enrollment (Zeman & Frenette, 2021). The increase in post-secondary graduates, especially at the undergraduate level, may indicate that we will have an upcoming increase in applications to graduate programs in Canada, including MLIS programs.

Investigating current post-secondary student trends in Canada based on Statistics Canada (2022) as shown in Table 1, year-over-year comparisons from 2016–2021 show a significant increase in science, STEM, and STEM-plus health science post-secondary enrollments. As of 2021, these groups constitute 14%, 38.5%, and 51%, respectively, of the Canadian post-secondary population and grow by at least 1% every year. In particular, science post-secondary enrollments are growing steadily, with a consistent growth rate of 4–6% since 2016, even with a decrease in overall post-secondary enrollment in 2020–2021. By comparison, enrollments in humanities have decreased over the last several years, and account for about 11.5% of post-secondary enrollments. Education accounts for a relatively stable 4.5%. This certainly implies that the Canadian post-secondary population is also not well represented by the current discipline representation in LIS, with science and STEM representation lagging at approximately one-third of its overall post-secondary value. Ironically, it appears that the representation of people with science backgrounds in science librarianship better represents the Canadian post-secondary population overall.

Table 1.

	2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020		2020/2021	
Total # of postsecondary enrollments	2,076,102		2,116,545		2,156,100		2,183,793		2,171,712	
% change			1.95%		1.87%		1.28%		-0.55%	
Field of Study	# enrolled	% of total								
Personal improvement and leisure [0]	20,853	1.00%	21,882	1.03%	22,494	1.04%	22,146	1.01%	14,700	0.68%
Education [1]	90,162	4.34%	88,878	4.20%	90,888	4.22%	93,900	4.30%	97,455	4.49%

Field of Study	# enrolled	% of total								
Visual and performing arts, and communications technologies [2]	79,014	3.81%	79,845	3.77%	80,622	3.74%	81,747	3.74%	80,082	3.69%
Humanities [3]	264,618	12.75%	259,485	12.26%	258,528	11.99%	252,570	11.57%	248,319	11.43%
Social and behavioural sciences and law [4]	282,627	13.61%	284,568	13.44%	287,478	13.33%	292,641	13.40%	301,494	13.88%
Business, management and public administration [5]	383,844	18.49%	397,872	18.80%	406,329	18.85%	417,924	19.14%	423,057	19.48%
Physical and life sciences and technologies [6]	169,329	8.16%	172,425	8.15%	174,351	8.09%	178,335	8.16%	182,766	8.42%
Mathematics, computer and information sciences [7]	80,820	3.89%	90,819	4.29%	101,334	4.70%	113,040	5.18%	120,714	5.56%
Architecture, engineering and related technologies [8]	224,523	10.81%	230,583	10.89%	233,271	10.82%	237,948	10.90%	231,285	10.65%
Agriculture, natural resources and conservation [9]	31,041	1.50%	32,499	1.54%	32,973	1.53%	33,801	1.55%	33,471	1.54%
Health and related fields [10]	260,745	12.56%	266,121	12.57%	268,401	12.45%	270,783	12.40%	273,561	12.60%
Personal, protective and transportation services [11]	42,771	2.06%	45,279	2.14%	47,454	2.20%	48,744	2.23%	48,387	2.23%
Other [12]	55,884	2.69%	57,174	2.70%	58,422	2.71%	56,679	2.60%	52,374	2.41%
Unclassified [13]	89,874	4.33%	89,112	4.21%	93,552	4.34%	83,538	3.83%	64,044	2.95%
STEM ([6], [7], [8])	474,672	36.48%	493,827	36.78%	508,956	36.94%	529,323	37.64%	534,765	38.51%
% change			4.04%		3.06%		4.00%		1.03%	

Field of Study	# enrolled	% of total								
Science + Math ([6], [7])	250,149	12.05%	263,244	12.44%	275,685	12.79%	291,375	13.34%	303,480	13.97%
% change			5.23%		4.73%		5.69%		4.15%	
STEM + Health ([6], [7], [8], [10])	735,417	49.04%	759,948	49.35%	777,357	49.39%	800,106	50.04%	808,326	51.10%
% change			3.34%		2.29%		2.93%		1.03%	

Table 1. Canadian post-secondary enrollment data per academic year and percent change between successive years. Data adapted from Statistics Canada (2022).

These disparities between MLIS programs, LIS professions, and the wider student population paint a dismal picture. While there is anecdotal evidence of improved science representation in LIS (Kuruppu, 2006), the current situation is not truly known as a benchmark for changes. Adding additional stress is the shortage of science librarians (Pellack, 2006), and so there is more demand for students with science backgrounds and fewer of them to fill that demand.

While much of the literature on science educational backgrounds in LIS is focused on the benefit or requirements of science librarianship, it is well established that science librarians do not need science backgrounds to perform their role (Beck & Callison, 2006; Hackenburg & Chu, 2002; Sterner, 2020). Fletcher (2015) provides an in-depth look at a specific example, and Fritzler (2006) provides guidance on how to adapt to science librarianship without a science background. This leads to the question of whether there are positions in LIS that require or benefit from MLIS graduates with science backgrounds. Even if a science background is not required, a science degree is typically preferred in about half of science librarian job postings (Sterner, 2020) and there is a lack of qualified applicants or a lack of applicants at all compared to equivalent positions with a humanities focus (Fletcher, 2015; Sterner, 2020; Walker, 2010). Sterner (2020) specifically notes that “it was easier to pull science/STEM majors into librarianship than librarians into science/STEM” (p. 447). Overall, the majority of science librarians feel that having a science background is important (Beck & Callison, 2006; Lo et al., 2015; Sterner, 2020), but having an MLIS is more important (Eells, 2006; Kuruppu, 2006). Having subject-specific knowledge in science librarianship is beneficial to the librarian as well as to their colleagues without a science background as they can assist in providing discipline-specific context and information (Raszewski, 2011). Sci-

ence librarians with a science background will start on the same footing with clientele in terms of scientific values, vocabulary, and methodology, have more confidence asking questions in reference interviews, and be more effective and efficient in researching in the field (Ard et al, 2006; Hallmark & Lembo, 2003).

There is also significant evidence that science librarianship has and will continue to change to incorporate or divide into new roles, such as data services librarians, to accommodate increasing research support in terms of data visualization, data analysis, systematic reviews, research collaboration, scientific writing, and communication (ACRL, 2022; Ard, 2006; Bishop et al., 2021; Bishop et al., 2023; Clarke & Kim, 2018; Dali & Caidi, 2016; Dennie, 2014; Kuruppu, 2006; Smith, 2006; Sterner, 2020). In particular, science librarians can help address research data management needs that have been placed on researchers, motivated by the current open science paradigm shift and the introduction of new research data policies at federal and funder levels (Bishop et al., 2021; Bishop et al., 2023). However, these roles and responsibilities illustrate a current gap in LIS practitioner knowledge (Dali & Caidi, 2016). Fortunately, working with data and being familiar with the context of the discipline and research area are both qualities and skill sets that MLIS graduates with science backgrounds can bring to the increasingly complex and diverse field of science librarianship.

Outside of traditional librarianship, there are other positions that benefit from MLIS graduates with science backgrounds. Unfortunately, non-library roles are hard to track despite at least 10% of MLIS graduates in the United States and Canada going into non-library positions (Weech & Konieczny, 2007), but one obvious area is information technology (Gordon, 2008). While specific positions might not be known, MLIS students with science backgrounds do distance themselves from the librarian label more than LIS students overall by using the label “information professional” (Walker, 2011), indicating a desire to not only be affiliated with library work and roles.

Motivations for Students with STEM Backgrounds to Enter an MLIS Program

It is established that the number of MLIS students and graduates with science backgrounds does not reflect the post-secondary population in Canada and that there is a need for MLIS graduates with science backgrounds in LIS. However, these facts are not motivations for students with STEM and applied science backgrounds to enter the profession. Investigating their motivations and how they compare and contrast with those of the general MLIS student

population can help identify gaps and areas for improved recruitment. After all, current MLIS students with science backgrounds, regardless of how few there are, represent recruitment success stories.

Before considering motivations for entering an MLIS program, it is important to consider career movement trends for STEM and applied science graduates more generally. From a study by Edwards et al. (2023) of 9000 STEM Ph.D. graduates in the United States between 2000–2008, we know that STEM graduates do not follow the traditional “pipeline” in academic research through to tenured professorship. Even of those who do hold positions in a tenure-track academic role, one-third did not follow the pipeline process of moving from undergraduate directly to graduate work, through postdoctoral fellowships and directly into a professor position—they worked outside academia and came back again. Edwards et al. (2023) did not analyze which positions were research-based or in which fields of work the positions ended up being. It is also relevant to consider that some of the tenure-track academic positions identified could be academic librarian positions.

Most studies addressing motivations for MLIS students with science backgrounds focus on MLIS student motivations to become science librarians, which simultaneously captures students who do not have science backgrounds and excludes students with science backgrounds who are not interested in becoming science librarians. The only study I found that addresses MLIS students directly without an assumption about their intended career is Walker’s (2011) study, which found that MLIS students with science backgrounds have the same or similar motivations to enroll in their program as their peers with no significant differences. It is still worth noting that exposure to science libraries and science librarians is a motivating factor, even though it tends to happen later in the student’s career (Eells, 2006; Sterner 2020).

Career changes are also consistent motivating factors, with mentions of negatives of current positions such as grant writing, job instability, poor work-life balance, pressures of a male-dominated field, and stress, exhaustion, and burnout (Hallmark & Lebo, 2003; Raszewski, 2011; Walker, 2011), as well as positives or attractors of LIS positions such as support for a love of scientific and technical literature, the challenge of information research, the variety of jobs, the ability to work with powerful cutting-edge technology and help clients, the encouragement of fascination with information explosion, and teamwork with faculty and researchers (Hallmark & Lembo, 2003; Raszewski, 2011; Sterner, 2020; Walker, 2011).

It is interesting to note that while the themes of career change as a

motivation are the same between MLIS students in general and those with a science background, the specific considerations differ. Students with science backgrounds appear to identify and specify the technology and research aspects of LIS more than MLIS students do in general, likely due to their initial scientific vocation. Additionally, a dramatic career change for MLIS students with a science background was often not the goal, with most feeling that they were not leaving science but applying it (Walker, 2011).

Recruitment of STEM Graduates to MLIS Programs

In general, as Ard (2006) put it, “contact with a librarian has the strongest impact on a student’s decision to join the profession” (p. 238) and is a top factor in surveys of both MLIS students overall and those with science backgrounds or aiming to be science librarians (Dukic, 2019; Hallmark & Lembo, 2003; Pellack, 2006). However, MLIS students tend to have no exposure to science libraries or alternative LIS roles (Eells, 2006; Piper & Wilairat, 2022).

Practical ways of increasing exposure while also actively benefiting students during their MLIS degree is by offering science librarianship courses in MLIS programs (Eells 2006; Ho et al., 2018; Piper & Wilairat, 2022) and inviting guest speakers into core MLIS courses (Smith, 2006). However, this does not help get students into the MLIS program in the first place. Making LIS more visible to high school and undergraduate students of varying disciplines will make opportunities more apparent (Harrick & Fullington, 2017; Moniarou-Papaconstantinou et al., 2015; Pellack, 2006). One demonstrated method to increase both exposure and experience in LIS as well as subject-specific LIS positions is undergraduate and graduate internships in LIS settings (Fletcher, 2015; Ho et al., 2018; Level & Blair, 2006). Harrick & Fullington (2017) and Lantzy & Matlin (2021) both provide an example of an undergraduate internship program for recruiting science librarians, exposing them to potential career paths and building their research skills simultaneously. Another option is postdoctoral fellowships in research libraries for new science Ph.D. graduates (Kuruppu, 2006), where new PhDs might find librarianship particularly interesting due to a depressed job market in their field (Lo et al., 2015) and might be likely to leave the traditional academic research pipeline at that point (Edwards et al., 2023).

Librarianship is also a common pathway for immigrants to Canada to get a meaningful credential fast that can also allow the transfer of existing skills, especially when their current credentials are not recognized (Lo et al., 2015). There may be an untapped pool of potential MLIS students with science back-

grounds who are actively looking for opportunities to integrate into the Canadian workforce.

A less-directed recruitment strategy could be providing valuable information about the LIS profession to undergraduate science students. In particular, recruiters could share what actual roles and responsibilities look like to help dispel incorrect assumptions about LIS (Kuruppu, 2006; Taylor et al., 2011), stress the relevance of both books and technology (Talyor et al., 2011), mention that librarianship positions typically have better salaries than science positions for people with an undergraduate science degree (Walker, 2011), and promote the flexibility of online programs (Smith, 2006), such as the medical librarian-specific online program showcased by Detlefsen (2004).

It is also worth noting that science librarianship is often a second or third career choice among librarians (Ortega & Brown, 2005; Raskewski, 2011; Winston, 2000), and so recruitment efforts need to be adapted and applied to various levels, ages, career stages, and occupations both within and outside LIS.

Conclusion

Upon entering MLIS programs, students tend to be in the process of changing careers and are motivated to pursue LIS professions due to a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic factors that are related to their cultural and current career context. Exposure to libraries and library work, whether general or science-specific, plays a key role in impacting the decisions of students with STEM backgrounds to enroll in an MLIS program. LIS as a field benefits from having educational and occupational diversity, which is a motivator to increase representation from people with science backgrounds, as they are currently underrepresented. Additionally, science librarianship benefits by having MLIS graduates with science backgrounds and it is expected that the increased complexity and data services focus of science librarianship may also be well served by those with STEM backgrounds. The availability of hybrid and online MLIS programs in Canada and the increasing diversity of LIS roles, specifically science librarianship roles, may be attractive factors to prospective MLIS students with science backgrounds. Recruitment suggestions for increasing the representation of students with science backgrounds in MLIS tend to be abstract suggestions or else would require substantial program investments, without many practical recommendations or real-life examples.

The current situation of MLIS students in Canada—their demographics, educational backgrounds, motivations, and aspirations—is not known. Future research is needed to understand the Canadian MLIS student population and

the needs of the LIS profession in Canada. From previous research, it can be estimated that the number of MLIS students and graduates with science backgrounds does not reflect the overall post-secondary population in Canada and that there is a need for MLIS graduates with science backgrounds in LIS in Canada. Knowing the true distribution of educational backgrounds, and especially those from science backgrounds, will be helpful in determining who is currently in MLIS programs, who should be in MLIS programs to better match our population and needs, and where and how recruitment efforts should be aimed to address this gap.

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